

FAT FROM THE SEEDS OF *VANGUERA SPINOSA* (N.O. RUBIACEAE)*

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The fat from the seeds of *Vanguera spinosa* contains an inseparable mixture of palmitic and stearic acids to the extent of 27.95% (the proportion of the two acids being 67.5% and 32.5 % respectively), oleic acid 32.46 % and linoleic acid 39.69 %.

The fact that the two solid acids could not be separated by the usual methods and I. V. accompanied by m. p. 50° are worth noting.

Vanguera spinosa (Marathi: Alu, Huloo; Hindi: Maina, Muduna) is distributed over North Bengal, Konkan, Deccan, Southern Maratha Country and North Kanare. The fruit is smooth, globose, about one inch in diameter, yellowish when ripe and edible.

EXPERIMENTAL

The seeds for this investigation were collected from a forest about 30 miles south-west of Kolhapur. The decorticated seeds were extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet, and the yield (38.5%) was calculated on this basis. The last traces of the solvent were removed by distillation under vacuum, whereupon the fat set to a semi-solid mass, which on warming on a water-bath, became thinner and transparent. The physical and chemical constants of this fat are given below.

TABLE I

Specific gravity at 24°/28°	.. 0.9515	Iodine value	.. 88.63
Refractive index at 26°	.. 1.4780	Reichert-Meiszel value	.. 1.56
Acid number	.. 3.9	Polenske number	.. 0.48
Saponification value	.. 190.75	Acetyl value	.. 5.8
		Unsaponifiable matter	.. 0.95 %

Insoluble Mixed Fatty Acids.—The fat was saponified with alcoholic potash, and the soap, after being washed with ether to remove the unsaponifiable matter, was decomposed with hydrochloric acid to liberate the fatty acids. The liberated acids were taken up with ether, washed free from the mineral acids and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Later, the ether was distilled off when the mixed fatty acids were left. The constants of these mixed fatty acids are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Yield.	Iodine value.	Acid number.	Mean M. W.
87%	103.2	201.7	277.65

According to this iodine value for the mixed fatty acids, that for the oil would be 89.32, which corresponds very well with the one actually found, namely 88.63.

The separation of the saturated and unsaturated fatty acids was effected by Twit-chell's lead-salt method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

* A note on this subject appeared previously (*Current Sci.*, 1942, 11, 400).

Mixed acids taken	..	39.34 g.
Solid acids obtained	..	10.96 g. (27.88%)
Liquid acids obtained	..	28.38 g. (72.14%)

Solid Fatty Acids.—The lead-salts of the saturated acids were decomposed with dilute nitric acid, and the liberated solid fatty acids were taken up with ether. The ether extract was washed with water till the washings were no longer acid to methyl orange. On the removal of the ether, the solid acids obtained gave the following values.

TABLE III

Iodine value	..	3.49	Mean molecular weight	..	267.6
Acid number	..	209.3	Melting point (crude)	..	52°

These crude solid acids (1.013 g.) on crystallisation from acetone gave the following fractions :

Fraction.	Wt.	M. p.	Fraction.	Wt.	M. p.
I	0.0884 g.	54-56°	V	0.0604 g.	54°
II	0.36	54-55°	VI	0.2672	54°
III	0.1174	54°	VII	0.056	54°
IV	0.0324	54°			

Excepting the first two fractions, the rest of them appear to be similar. Their mixed melting points with myristic, palmitic and stearic acids are given below :

With	Mixed melting point.
Myristic acid	47°
Palmitic acid	56°
Stearic acid	62°

This, and the fact that these solid acids have the mean molecular weight of 267-268 (as against 228 of myristic acid) rule out the possibility of fractions III to VII being exclusively those of myristic acid.

Another possibility is that, they may be identical with the so-called daturic acid ($C_{17}H_{34}O_2$), which is reported to have melting points varying from 54° to 59° and a mean molecular weight of 270 (Giraud, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1890, 9, 1137). Its identity as an individual acid was first reported by Meyer and Beer (*Monatsh.*, 1910, 31, 1239) by isolating it from Datura oil itself. It was, however, later found to be an equimolecular mixture of palmitic and stearic acids (Verkade and Coops, *Biochem. Z.*, 1929, 206, 468; Manjunath and Siddappa, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 400). Zinc salt of this acid was found by Meyer and Beer (*loc. cit.*) to melt at 126.6° (benzene).

Zinc salt of the saturated fatty acids obtained in the present investigation was sparingly soluble in boiling benzene and the crystallised salt melted at 119-20°. Katti and Puntambekar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 225) reported a similar salt with m.p. 119-20°, obtained from a fraction of saturated acids from the seeds of *Caesalpinia Bonducellia*.

Methyl esters of these mixed solid acids were prepared and then distilled under 15-20 mm. pressure. All the quantity came over between 180° and 183°. These gave the values noted in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Solidifying point	..	25-26°
Saponification value	..	198.5
Mean molecular weight	..	282.1

TABLE V

Acid number	..	211.08
Mean molecular weight	..	265.4
Melting point	..	54-55°

From these esters original acids were recovered which gave values shown in Table V. These figures (Table V) are similar to those obtained for the original acids, i.e. M. W. 267.6, and m.p. 54°.

Next, potassium salts of the mixed acids were prepared and crystallised from acetone. The various fractions were collected and the acids recovered from these fractions separately were found to have 54° as their melting point.

About 0.5 g. of the acids was dissolved in boiling alcohol and to this was added a boiling alcoholic solution of magnesium acetate, containing just enough salt to precipitate half the amount of the acid into its salt. The melting points of the acids recovered from the precipitated salt and of those from the filtrate did not vary, it being 54-55° in both the cases.

Such mixtures have been reported by many workers. Verkade and Coops (*loc. cit.*) subjected the methyl esters of the solid acids from the oil of *Datura stramonium* (the so-called daturic acid) to fractional distillation in vacuum and from a comparative study of the melting points of acids obtained from various fractions, with those of the acids from artificial mixtures of the methyl esters of stearic and palmitic acids, they concluded that the "daturic acid" was really a mixture of stearic and palmitic acids. Manjunath and Siddappa (*loc. cit.*) by intensive fractionation of the methyl esters of these acids found that they consisted of palmitic and stearic acids. Katti and Manjunath (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 842) also obtained a similar acid in lower fractions of the saturated fatty acids from the oil from the seeds of *Butea frondosa*. Further, Puntambekar and Katti (*loc. cit.*) obtained, together with palmitic and stearic acids, a similar acid (M. W. 270-272; m.p. 55-56°) in the intermediate fractions. The saturated acids, obtained during the present investigation, appear in all probability to be a mixture of palmitic and stearic acids of a similar type.

The percentage composition of this mixture, calculated on the basis of its molecular weight (265.4) works out to be 67.86% palmitic and 32.14% stearic acids. A mixture of the two acids melting at 54.5° has been reported by Hehner and Mitchell to consist of 67.5% palmitic and 32.5% stearic acids (Lewkowitsch, "Laboratory Companion to Oils and Fats Industry," p. 94). These values correspond well with the values obtained above. To confirm this further (assuming a mixture of 70% palmitic and 30% stearic acids) to the solid acids obtained, a known amount of pure stearic acid was added so as to make it a mixture with definite proportions as follows, and the melting points of different mixtures noted (Table VI),

TABLE VI

Composition.	Melting point
I. Original (assuming 70% palmitic and 30% stearic)	54°
II. 50% palmitic and 50% stearic (by adding 0.08 g. stearic acid to 0.2 g. mixture)	57°-58°
III. 20% palmitic and 80% stearic (by adding 0.25 g. stearic acid to 0.1 g. mixture)	63°-64°

These melting points agree well with the values given by Hehner and Mitchell (*loc. cit.*).

Attempts were then made to prepare artificially such an inseparable mixture of the two acids by mixing 3.643 g. of pure palmitic acid with 1.607 g. of pure stearic acid. The mixture was kept in a sealed tube and melted by placing the tube in a hot water-bath. The contents of the tube were then shaken vigorously and left for a couple of days. A portion of this mixture was fractionally crystallised from pure acetone. The first fraction on further crystallisations gave pure stearic acid (m. p. 69°) and the last one yielded pure palmitic acid (m. p. 62°). About 1g. of the mixture was converted separately into its calcium, barium, and lead salts in the usual manner and the acids were recovered from the salts. The two component acids could be separated from these by fractional crystallisation from acetone.

Methyl esters of pure palmitic and stearic acids were next prepared separately and the two were mixed in calculated amounts so as to give ultimately a mixture of the two acids in desired proportion (70:30). Thus 7.384 g. of palmitic acid ester were mixed with 3.148 g. of stearic acid ester to form a complete homogeneous mixture and sealed in a tube. This tube was placed in a hot water-bath and was shaken vigorously and kept overnight. The mixture was then distilled fractionally under reduced pressure. The esters came over in four fractions between 220° and 234°. The fractions were saponified and the fatty acids liberated in the usual manner and were fractionally crystallised from acetone. The later fractions from the first two gave a melting point of 62° and their mixed melting point with an authentic sample of palmitic acid remained unchanged. The first fraction from the last lot had m. p. 65° which rose to 69° on further recrystallisation. No depression was noted in its mixed melting point with an authentic sample of stearic acid.

Similarly, an artificial mixture of ethyl esters of the two acids was prepared (4.646 g. of palmitic acid ester and 2.194 g. of stearic acid ester) and treated in exactly the same manner as the mixtures of methyl esters above. Finally the two acids could be separated in this case also.

Since stearic acid can be steam distilled without decomposition, a certain quantity of the total acids (solid) obtained from the fat under investigation, was steam-distilled. From the distillate was obtained a solid which melted at 60° (crude) and finally after recrystallisation gave a melting point of 65-66°. This was found identical with stearic acid by mixed m. p. Then a much small portion of the total solid acids was again steam-distilled for a long time; the residue, after repeated crystallisation gave an acid which was identical with palmitic acid (confirmed by mixed m. p.). Thus qualitatively the two component solid acids (stearic and palmitic) were separated from this very intimate mixture of the total solid acids.

Unsaturated Fatty Acids.—These acids were liberated from the liquid lead salts with dilute hydrochloric acid, and were taken up with ether. The ethereal solution of

these acids was washed free from hydrochloric acid and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate overnight. Next day the ether was removed by distillation completely, and the acids thus obtained gave the following values.

TABLE VII

Iodine value	Acid number	Mean M. W.
145.4	197.95	283.05

According to this iodine value for the mixed liquid acids, that for the total mixed fatty acids would work out to 104.8, whereas the actual value is 103.2.

Bromination of Liquid Acids.—The acids (12.837 g.) were dissolved in 50 c.c. glacial acetic acid. Bromine was dissolved separately in an equal volume of glacial acetic acid, and the two were kept in an ice-box for a while. The bromine solution was then added to the acid solution gradually with constant stirring till the colour of bromine persisted. Except for shaking, the flask was kept in ice all along. The reaction mixture was left in the ice-box overnight, when a white crystalline solid separated. The solution was filtered, and the solid left behind was washed and recrystallised from alcohol. The filtrate was poured into water and washed free from the acetic acid. The residual mass was rubbed with petroleum ether for a long time, but no further solid compound separated out. The petroleum ether solution was then washed with a dilute solution of sodium thiosulphate to remove free bromine, if any, and then it was dried thoroughly. The petroleum ether was then distilled off, when the liquid bromo derivative was obtained. The bromine in both these derivatives was estimated. The solid bromo derivative (m. p. 112-13°) contained 52.16% and the liquid bromo derivative, 35.22% bromine. The former corresponds to linoleic tetrabromide m. p. 114° (Br, 53.33%) and the latter to oleic dibromide (Br, 36.18 %).

The unsaturated acids (12.837 g.) gave 15.18 g. of linoleic tetrabromide, and 9.051 g. of oleic dibromide. These quantities correspond respectively to 7.063 g. linoleic acid, and 5.774 g. oleic acid. Thus their percentages are 55 and 45 respectively. On this basis, the iodine value of the mixed liquid acids and that for the total mixed fatty acids work out to 142.62 and 102.7 respectively, whereas those actually obtained are 145.4 and 103.2. The mixed melting point of linoleic tetrabromide obtained with an authentic sample of the same was 112-13°

Oxidation of Liquid Acids.—A portion of the mixed liquid acids was oxidised with potassium permanganate in an alkaline solution by the method of Hazura (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats, and Waxes," Edn VI, Vol. I, p. 575). The acids were saponified with alcoholic potash and the soaps formed were dissolved in water after distilling off the alcohol. To this solution was added about 1.5 % cold potassium permanganate solution in a thin stream with constant stirring, till the lather formed at the top showed a pink tinge. The solution was then allowed to stand overnight. It was then acidified with sulphurous acid till all the hydrated manganese peroxide was dissolved, and the solution became colourless and acidic. A white flocculent precipitate was obtained.

The precipitated acids were first washed with water and then with petroleum ether to remove the unoxidised acids, if any. They were then extracted with a large amount of ether and filtered. The filtrate gave a white solid, m. p. 127-28°. This, on recrystallisation from alcohol, melted at 130-31°. It was dihydroxystearic acid.

The residue, insoluble in ether, was dissolved in hot alcohol and crystallised, when a white solid (m.p. 157-58°) was obtained. This is probably the tetrahydroxystearic acid which is reported to exist in various isomeric forms and whose melting points vary between 155° and 180° (Katti and Puntambekar, *loc. cit.* Krishna and Puntambekar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 304). No acid was detected in the filtrate after the removal of the above two acids. This confirms that only oleic and linoleic acids are present in the unsaturated acids.

Thus the percentages of the fatty acids contained in the fat are: palmitic and stearic acids (forming a very intimate mixture), 27.85; oleic acid, 32.46; linoleic acid, 39.69.

Unsaponifiable Matter.—The ethereal washings of the potassium soaps of the fat were washed with water completely. The ether was then evaporated when a white solid was obtained. This was crystallised from hot alcohol. The solid that separated on cooling was wax-like and melted at 56-58°. It was insoluble in concentrated sulphuric acid. It may be a saturated hydrocarbon.

The filtrate later gave a white substance, m.p. 205-210°. On viewing through a microscope, needle shaped crystals were observed. It dissolved in cold concentrated sulphuric acid, giving the solution a pink colour, thereby indicating that it was a sterol. Its acetate melted at 62-63°.

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